

EARLY CRUSADING MOVEMENTS AND THEIR PROCESSES OF WAGING WAR

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Annotation: This article contains information about the actions of the initial crusade and the events of the first crusade, which includes the sermon of the pope of the Catholic Church and the crowd of peasants and the political processes that preceded the conquest of Jerusalem, which is considered the Holy Land, the lifestyle of the ordinary population at this time, as well as information and

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The beginning of the first crusades dates back to 1096. We know these marches began after the call of the Catholic Church and the fiery sermon of Pope Urban II. The Cathedral of the church was held in Clermont, southern France, on 18-25 November 1095, under Pope Urban II. After the official part was closed on November 27 in a field near the city, in the open air, in front of priests and ordinary people of different classes, the pope gave a fiery sermon in which he called on the Frankish Knights to free Christians from the Muslim siege and reclaim the Holy Sepulchre in Jerusalem from the infidels. [1. p-10-11]

He calls everyone to crusade to free the "Tomb of the Prophet". The pope does not forget to take part in the processions and forgive the sins of the fallen, to remind them of the riches of the East in the other world; to promise that "whoever is here in grief and poverty will be there rich".

Jerusalem is described by the Lord of the Earth, the Paradise Land, in which milk and honey flow as rivers. The crowd shouted " This Is God's desire!", and it is here that they begin to sew on their clothes The Shape of an idol made of fabric. [2. P-128]

It can be seen that this speech of the pope came in different interpretations in different sources and literature. But their ideological meaning was one, and the pope and the Catholic Church became religious in order to start these campaigns faster. Jerusalem urges the earth to start raiding campaigns here as the Paradise Land of the Earth. After these events, the initial Harkats began to organize the first crusades. All took part in these walks in the way of their own goals. For example, after the call of the pope is widely spread, large owners see a means of increasing their wealth on walks. The petty and middle Knights, on the other hand, are those who dream of achieving large estates, and for this reason also take part in these marches. Dependent peasants considered the goal of land and freedom from their participation in these marches. All those who tried to use these walks in the way of their own goals.

The initial (April–October 1096) was the first stage of the First Crusade, and the march lasted from April 1096 to octabre. The march began a few months before Urban II's decision of 15 August 1096. On the eve of the crusade, Europe was plagued by plague and famine. As a result, many people were impoverished, and they saw participation in the crusade as a one-to-one way to improve their economic status. In addition, the lunar eclipse of 1095, the meteor shower, and other events were perceived as a gesture to the success of the March. The crusade aroused great interest in Western Europe, and various sources say that about 300,000 people attended. Women and children were also involved in the March. [3. P-267]

As the Crusades noted above, all the layers involved in these marches participated in the cause of their own benefit and purpose. It would not be a

mistake to say that the plague epidemic and famine that spread across Europe shook the population also caused these marches to be organized in a hurry. In addition the Catholic Church has given the people a religious idea, and through the occurrence of phenomena of different nature, the people take these reasons as a sign that we will start walking. The man who thought of these events and the preaching of the pope was in a hurry to participate in these processions.

For this reason, the crusade has aroused great enthusiasm in Western Europe, with many individuals including Even women and children. The Kings did not participate in the first crusade. At first, the peasants begin to walk. It was attended by counts, dukes and princes.

While the crusade of 1096, organized by a crowd, began to prepare for the March, a regular army composed of Knights gathered from various European lands. Count Raymund Tuluzsky, together with the Papal Legate Ademar Monteilsky and Bishop Le-Peui, commanded the Sares of Provence, Prince Boumend Tarentsky and his cousin Tancred commanded the Normans of Southern Italy, Brothers Gottfried, Estash and Baldwin Bulonsky commanded the lotharingians, Robert Flandriysky, Robert Normandsky, count Stephen Bluasky and Hugo Vermandau (younger brother of Philip I of France) commanded the Knights of northern France. [3. P-270]

While the Kings were not involved in the early crusades, the inhabitants and Knights from various European lands were commanded by the Papal Legate, the bishop, the prince and the counts in the Crusades. The Crusades were so rapidly spread throughout Europe that the number of participants in it would increase day after day after the call of the pope.

In the spring of 1096, part of Northern and eastern France set out for the crusade of the peasant masses of West Germany. The peasants, whose sheep were stuffed with puch nuts, were led by the monk Pyotr Amensky (Pyotr Pustinnik) and the small owner Knight Walter Goliak. [4. P-180]

The peasants, who had benefited from the Crusades, had no tolerance to wait for the Knights 'March, which began in the late following summer, and the army, eaten from the peasants, crowded with the Crusader peasants' families in an irregular, ill-armed manner to begin the initial marches, and set off with many loaded carts.

The marches were accompanied by various tramp and vagrant, half-robber Knights who would take the initiative to rob the natives on the way, and the Crusaders would massacre the Jews who lived in the towns on their way.

Pyotr Amensky's followers repressed Jews in the cities of Rouen and Cologne. Jews from Trier, Mainz, Speyer and worms on the Rhine were also plundered. The "Solomon bar Simeon" Chronicle states that "one man would kill his brother, another his parents, and the parents 'child". Despite attempts by local clergy and government officials to stop the massacre, thousands of Jews were killed by the Crusaders. In an attempt to justify their actions, the Crusaders made evidence of Urban II's speech with a sword in the Cathedral of Clermont, about subjugating not only Muslims, but also all people of religion other than Christians.[3. P-268]

The reason why the Crusaders massacred the Jews without fault was not Pope Urban II's speech at the cathedral. Because in this cathedral, the Catholic Church had insisted that the peaceful population should not be massacred and converted to Christianity without killing all people of other religions. But the peasants, tired of torture, thought that something faster in the imagination of the Knights would free Jerusalem from the unbelievers and have the "Tomb of the Prophet" there and New Lands. Many sources cite that this was the way the Crusaders did to free the "Tomb of the prophet" from the unbelievers. But in my opinion this reason was an excuse.

Their original purpose was to occupy the "Holy Land" as described by representatives of the Catholic Church, to quickly gain access to New Lands and

solve all the obstacles and problems that came out of their way so that they could be freed from dependence, to quickly land on new lands and live life in roxate.

The Crusader peasants on the highway were not regularly supplied with food. For this reason, the Crusaders, forced to find food by force, suffer severe casualties from the troops who came out defending their people in Hungary and Bulgaria, while some units are completely exterminated. Only half of the Crusaders arrive in Constantinople at the end of the summer of 1096. It is no secret that the peasant walk in general is meaningless.

When a crowd of Crusaders arrived in Constantinople, the emperor had learned of their deeds until their arrival. The emperor threatens the Crusaders to show chaos and violence, and rushes to send them off to the coast of Asia Minor. On the coast of Asia Minor, the Crusader crowd soon clashes with Turkish troops, and they crush most of the Crusaders. Thus, the Crusaders ' march East was completely defeated.

In the autumn of 1096, Knights, mostly French and Italian Knights, partly West German knights departed. This March was led by The Duke of lower Lotharingia, Gottfried Bulonsky, who took Yevstafiy with him to the East with his two brothers — Baldwin. The French fiefs in the North were led by Robert, count of Normandy and Robert, count of Flanders, while the French fiefs in the South took Raymond, count of Toulouse, as their guide. One of the southern French Bishops, Bishop Ademar, who was made a papal representative (Legate) of the church, accompanied them. Duke Boemund of tarentia commanded the south Italian feudal lords, while his nephew count Tancred accompanied him [5. P-360].

The army, made up of feudal lords, was led by the above-mentioned figures in the Crusades. The total number of troops leaving Constantinople was 300,000. Given that there were also about 300,000 other black workers, women and children serving the army, in any case, the total number of Crusaders exceeded

half a million.

The Knights also went east through Constantinople, but in different ways. A variety of troops gathered in Constantinople along four routes. Gottfried and Baldwin crossed the Danube Valley with their troops and other German units from Hungary, Serbia and Bulgaria. On the way, clashes broke out with the local army. The party was the first to arrive in Constantinople and stood outside the city throughout the winter. Bishop Ademar, count Raymund and others set out from southern France and arrived in Constantinople via Northern Italy. Guga, both Robert and Étienne set out from England and northern France with their army and crossed the Alps and marched south across Italy. Leaving his companions to winter in southern Italy, the ship Hugo, sailing towards Constantinople, was wrecked, rescued by the Byzantines and sent to the capital. Hugo remained a hostage under the emperor. In the spring, both Robert and Étienne crossed the Adriatic and stopped at Durasso, heading for Constantinople. Through the same route, an army of Normans from Sicily by Boumand and Tanred also marched. [4. P-181]

In total, about 30-40 thousand Knights took part in the first march. But in their presence there were also many men-at-arms, servants, merchants of all kinds, and peasant armies that survived the first crusade also came and joined the Knights. The Crusades were carefully prepared . For this reason, we can see-that they divided into four groups and did so in order to reach their destination faster. The number of Crusaders reaching Constantinople through various routes reaches 300,000.

It was not until the spring of 1097 that the feudal-Crusaders, who had completely gathered in Constantinople, refused to swear an oath to the Byzantine emperor and remained stubborn for a long time. The Crusaders did not want to promise before the emperor that they would give Byzantium the lands that would be warred from the Turks in the East. Although the Knights did not think to

finally go over their promises from Zim, every tin was sworn. [5. P-361]

The Crusaders swore an oath telling Alexei that the territories to be invaded would be transferred to the Byzantine Empire. But the feudal lord in charge of his division did not want to submit to another and acted independently. All used this walk on the way to their goal.

In April 1097, the Crusaders passed through the Bosphorus. Crusaders crossing Asia Minor suffered severely from heat and dehydration. Some died unable to cope with the difficulties, many horses were slaughtered. In the summer of 1097, the Knights ' army was transferred to Asia Minor. Here, the Crusaders majacted the Turks in a battle next to Dorileia, after which they marched southeast towards Palestine. In the unbearable heat, the passage through the mountain roads was extremely laborious for them. Many of the Crusaders were killed on the way. [4. P-182]

For those who participated in the crusade, these campaigns were not easy. It was hard for them to cross the mountainous roads in the heat of the heat. This was because the Crusaders were exhausted from wars. But they were still moving on this path towards their goal. Such an unbearable hot despite the heat they head towards Palestine. The Crusaders would make ends meet in exchange for local Christians and funds sent from their lands. But they often met the demand needs of the destinations they encountered on their roads. Baldwin Bulonsky left the Crusader line and arrived in Edessa via Cilicia in early 1098, and was appointed as its successor in the confidence of the local ruler Tortosa. In the same year, Tortosa was killed by the edessians, while Baldwin remained ruler of the first crusader state. [3. P- 271]

The Crusader conquest of Edessa was important in terms of strategy, as Edessa was guarding Syria and Palestine from the north against a Turkish invasion. In the summer of 1098, the Crusaders captured the "capital of the East" — Antioch, with Boemund Tarensky taking control of Antioch as Duke. The third

major feudatory, Raymund Tuluzsky, was touched by the Tripoli Oblast (south of Antioch).

Finally, in the summer of 1099, the Crusaders reached Jerusalem. On 15 July 1099, they captured Jerusalem with shturm. The Crusaders plundered the city hard and brutally massacred a large part of its population, both Muslims and Christians, without ayamay. As a result of these invasions, the Crusaders took over the entire eastern coast of the Mediterranean, namely the former Phoenicia, Syria and Palestine. The cities of Jerusalem, Antioch, Tripoli, Edessa, Tyre, Sidon, acre fell to them. The length of the Crusader possessions, which stretched in a narrow region from North to South, reached 1200 km.

Thus, the first crusades ended with the occupation of Jerusalem and several cities. The real essence of the Crusades was the liberation of the “Holy Land” from the infidels. But this was not the goal of the Catholic Church, too, to participate in this March. All of these walks took part in the path of their intention. The Catholic Church has reached its intentions. The city of Jerusalem was seized as a result of prolonged attacks and incessant warfare. The invaders brutally tortured and killed Muslims, Jews and Christians alike. They did not spare men, women without sins and small children either.

When we judge these processions from the outside, it is like processions organized not to free the Holy Sepulchre, but to destroy the unbelievers. But the Crusaders lose their minds for this land to such an extent that they even kill their Christian Brothers. Survivors are awarded by participating in the March. The leaders of the gang become princes of large lands. Peasants were allocated lands with good conditions, and some were given Knightly titles for lack of Knights.

In conclusion, the “Tomb of the Prophet”, which the Crusaders tried to occupy with all their might, became uninterested after the capture of Jerusalem. One of the biggest reasons that prompted the start of this walk was this grave. But after the Holy steps were achieved, the Kingdom of Jerusalem was formed here.

At the cost of significant losses, the Catholic Church achieved its original goal. How many ordinary residents were tortured because of the walk. Young children have perished saying that women will participate in these walks. The Catholic Church and the Crusaders achieved all the goals they could think of. With this, the first crusades came to an end.

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